

Optimization of Connecting Rod for Materials Using ANSYS Analysis

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Abstract: The connecting rod for an automotive engine is a crucial part that is produced in large quantities. It transmits the piston's thrust to the crankshaft by joining a reciprocating piston to a revolving crankshaft. Depending on the engine's cylinder count, any car with an internal combustion engine needs at least one connecting rod. Automotive connecting rods are usually made by forging either powdered metal or wrought steel. They might be cast, too. However, blowholes in castings might be harmful from the perspectives of fatigue and durability. In order to compare & optimize materials for connecting rods, results of static structural analysis of connecting rod made of structural steel (conventional materials) have been compared with similar analysis of connecting rod using alternate materials. For the analysis several materials like Epoxy Carbon, Inconel 25, Inconel 718, & Titanium Alloy are being used. Considering all the above observations it can be concluded that Inconel materials can prove to enhance the performance of connecting rod because of better load bearing capacity in terms of its mechanical properties. Although the weight reduction can be achieved if Epoxy Carbon or Titanium alloy is used. But it has to be kept in mind that Titanium alloy is a costly material.

Keywords: Connecting Rod, IC engine, Optimization, stress distribution, deformation

I. Introduction

The connecting rod for an automotive engine is a crucial part that is produced in large quantities. It transmits the piston's thrust to the crankshaft by joining a reciprocating piston to a revolving crankshaft. Depending on the engine's cylinder count, any car with an internal combustion engine needs at least one connecting rod. Automotive connecting rods are usually made by forging either powdered metal or wrought steel. They might be cast, too. However, blowholes in castings might be harmful from the perspectives of fatigue and durability.

It makes sense that optimizing the connecting rod for weight or volume would lead to significant cost savings because of its high production volume. Additionally, it can accomplish the goal of lowering the engine component's weight, which will lower inertia loads, lower engine weight, and enhance engine efficiency and performance.

As a connecting rod revolves around the crankshaft and goes up and down, the angle between it and the piston might alter because the rod can rotate at both ends.

Carbon steel, iron base sintered metal, micro-alloyed steel, and spheroidized graphite cast iron are just a few of the many materials utilized to join rods. The connecting rods of automobile engines that are manufactured in large quantities are typically composed of steel. "Billet" connecting rods, which are machined from a solid metal billet instead of being cast or forged, can be utilized in high performance applications.

Other materials that are used for light weight and great impact absorption at the sacrifice of durability are T6-2024 Aluminium alloy and T651-7075 Aluminium alloy. Although titanium is more costly, it weighs less. For less expensive but less effective uses, such motor scooters, cast iron can be utilized.

Design optimization, which is frequently used synonymously with engineering optimization, uses mathematical optimization techniques to the formulation of design problems. A multi-objective optimization problem arises when the objective function f is a vector instead of a scalar. The global optimum is

found using global optimization techniques if there are multiple mathematical solutions to the design optimization problem.

II. Analysis of Connected Rod

One of the greatest modelling-related programs in the world, Solidworks-2020, is used to first model each component of the connecting rod independently in order to analyze it. The big end, small end, bolt, and nut are the four components that make up the connecting rod assembly. After modelling, all of these parts are put together using Solidworks-2020's assembly design module.

The connecting rod assembly is saved in either STEP (.step or .stp) or IGES (.iges or .igs) formats following modelling and assembly. The processes necessary for the connecting rod analysis are listed below-

- Start the analysis process of this model in ANSYS through selecting the static structural icon in modules list.
- Select connecting rod material gray cast iron.

Insert the properties of the material.

Fig. 1 Material properties

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- Import the geometry already developed in Solidworks-2020

Fig. 2- Geometry of Connecting Rod

- Apply the material to this component

Fig 3- Material of Connecting Rod

- Apply coordinate system to the component. By default, a global coordinate system is provided by the ANSYS itself but, if necessary, user can also apply or insert a new coordinate system at his/her will-

Fig 4- Coordinate system applied on the Connecting Rod

- Apply meshing to the component. If any other option is not selected & only mesh is generated then a mesh with default settings is generated but if one requires getting precise results then he/she must apply some special meshing methods & sizing. this is done in this study as follows-

Fig 5- meshing performed on Connecting Rod

Because of tetrahedrons methods & special sizing of element size of 1 mm is being applied, total numbers of nodes generated here is 157059 & total elements are equal to 84527.

- After completing the meshing step, boundary conditions are applied to the component. In this study total two boundary conditions are applied which are fixed support at the big end of this component & force of 20000 N.

Fig. 6- Boundary condition applied on Connecting Rod

- Now run the analysis.
- Find the outcomes & analyze the data for behaviour identification.

Static Structural Analysis of Connecting Rod

Here primary criteria were to evaluate & validate the equivalent stress generated on the connecting rod upon applying the load hence equivalent stress (Von-mises stress) was requested for solution. Apart from stress, several other parameters are also evaluated in the current research. The equivalent (von-mises) stress distribution pattern for this study under given inputs is as follows-

Fig. 7- Equivalent stress distribution

Now for further study total deformation, maximum principal stress, Normal Stress, Equivalent Elastic Strain & Normal Elastic Strain distribution has also been requested. The results are as follows-

Fig. 8- Total deformation distribution

Here we can see that maximum total deformation takes place near the outer portion of the disc brake & its numerical value being equal to 0.2035 mm.

Fig. 9– Maximum principal stress distribution

Maximum principal stress distribution reveals that maximum amount of maximum principal stress generated in the component is 670.76 MPa.

Fig. 10– Normal Stress distribution

Normal Stress distribution reveals that maximum amount of Normal stress generated in this component is 236.5 MPa. The findings of Gray cast iron connecting rod on ANSYS are being tabulated for further reference-

Table 1- Result table

S. No.	Specification	Value
1	Material used	Gray Cast Iron
2	Equivalent (von-mises) stress	849.92 MPa
3	Total Deformation	0.27094 mm
4	Maximum Principal Stress	856.2 MPa
5	Normal Stress	252.59 MPa
8	Weight	0.394 kg

All the results are being presented here in tabular form for reference-

Table 2- Result set for all the alternate materials

Material	Weight (kg)	Total Deformation (mm)	Equi. Stress (MPa)	Max. Prin. Stress (MPa)	Normal Stress (MPa)
Epoxy Carbon	0.082	3.482	874.92	870.1	385.93
Inconel 625	0.462	0.18407	692.57	742.84	232.57
Inconel 718	0.450	0.18034	685.08	744.35	240.47
Titanium Alloy	0.253	0.30746	815.8	816.38	291.23

III. Data Analysis & Interpretation

Weight pattern

Fig. 11- Weight pattern

The plot of weight for all the materials have been plotted in above figure. Here one can clearly see that for Conventional material, the weight of connecting rod is 0.394 kg which significantly reduces for Epoxy Carbon & Titanium Alloy. Inconel material exhibit slightly more weight than the conventional material (Gray Cast Iron). Hence this weight comparison plot shows that composite materials & Titanium Alloy are better suitable for connecting rod according to weight criteria. Although if we use Inconel materials, performance will not alter significantly as the weight of Inconel materials is approximately equal to that of conventional material (Gray Cast Iron).

Equivalent Stress Pattern

The plot of equivalent stress for all the materials have been plotted in below figure. Here one can clearly see that for conventional material (Gray Cast Iron), the equivalent stress of connecting rod is 849.92 MPa which increases slightly for Epoxy Carbon & reduces for Inconel materials. Titanium Alloys are also exhibiting little bit lesser equivalent stress as compared to conventional material. Hence this equivalent stress comparison plot shows that all the materials except composite materials are better suitable for connecting rod according to this criterion.

Fig. 12- Equivalent Stress Pattern

Total Deformation Pattern

Fig. 13- Total Deformation Pattern

The plot of total deformation for all the materials have been plotted in above figure. Here one can clearly see that for conventional material (Gray Cast Iron), the total deformation of connecting rod is 0.27094 mm which remains approximately equal for all the materials except composites. Hence this total deformation comparison plot shows that all the materials except composites are better suitable for connecting rod.

Maximum Principal Stress Pattern

The plot of Maximum Principal Stress for all the materials have been plotted in below figure. Here one can clearly see that for conventional material (Gray Cast Iron), the equivalent stress of connecting rod is 856.2 MPa which increases slightly for Epoxy Carbon & reduces for Inconel materials. Titanium Alloys are also exhibiting little bit lesser equivalent stress as compared to conventional material. Hence this Maximum Principal Stress comparison plot shows that all the materials except composite materials are better suitable for connecting rod according to this criterion.

Fig. 14- Maximum Principal Stress Pattern

Normal Stress Pattern

Fig. 15- Normal Stress Pattern

The plot of Normal Stress for all the materials have been plotted in below figure. Here one can clearly see that for conventional material (Gray Cast Iron), the Normal stress of connecting rod is 252.59 MPa which increases for Epoxy Carbon & reduces for Inconel materials. Titanium Alloys are also exhibiting little bit higher normal stress as compared to conventional material. Hence this Normal Stress comparison plot shows that all the materials except composite materials are better suitable for connecting rod according to this criterion.

IV. Conclusion

Current research analysis is focused on designing & optimizing the connecting rod used in the Internal Combustion Engines for different materials using some performance parameters. Numerous analyses were performed for the purpose and data was interpreted in the last chapter. On the basis of data interpretation in the last chapter following observations are being drawn-

- Weight comparison plot shows that Epoxy Carbon and Titanium Alloys are better suitable for connecting rod according to weight criteria. Although if we use Inconel materials, performance will not alter significantly as the weight of Inconel materials is approximately equal to that of conventional material (Gray Cast Iron).
- Equivalent stress comparison plot shows that all the materials except composite materials are better suitable for connecting rod according to this criterion.
- Total deformation comparison plot shows that all the materials except composites are better suitable for connecting rod.
- Maximum principal stress comparison plot shows that all the materials are suitable for connecting rod according to maximum principal stress criteria.
- Normal stress comparison plot shows that Inconel materials & all other materials except composites are better suitable for connecting rod according to normal stress criteria.

Considering all the above observations it can be concluded that Inconel materials can prove to enhance the performance of connecting rod because of better load bearing capacity in terms of its mechanical properties. Although the weight reduction can be achieved if aluminium alloy, Ti-Al 4V or Titanium alloy is used. But it has to be kept in mind that Titanium alloy is a costly material.

V. Future Scope

No study is finished on its own, and there is always room for improvement. The following are some ideas for futuristic researchers to consider:

- Future researchers can choose to use transient analysis, thermal performance, etc. for the connecting rods, as only the mechanical properties have been examined in the current study using static structural analysis.
- More recent materials must be examined and compared under a variety of robust conditions in order to generalize the findings.

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